

The Unseen Root: Re-Treatment of a Biradicular Mandibular Second Premolar

Shefali Singh¹, Parul Bansal², Ankusha Arora³, Kritika Rajoria⁴

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Postgraduate Student¹
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre
Ghaziabad

Professor & Head²
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre
Ghaziabad

Postgraduate Student³
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre
Ghaziabad

Postgraduate Student⁴
Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics
Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College and Research Centre
Ghaziabad

Abstract

Mandibular second premolars are typically considered single rooted and single canaled teeth, but anatomical variations can present significant endodontic challenges, especially in re-treatment cases. This case report presents the conservative re-treatment of tooth 45 in a 65 year old female with persistent post operative pain. Radiographic evaluation revealed a missed root and canal, along with associated periapical pathology. Upon re-treatment, two distinct roots with one canal each were identified. The case highlights the importance of recognizing rare anatomical variations and using a biologically guided approach to ensure successful outcomes.

Keywords: Two rooted premolar, Re-treatment, Mandibular Second Premolar, Missed Canal, Bioceramic sealer

Introduction

Anatomical variations in root canal morphology are critical determinants of endodontic success, particularly in retreatment cases. Variations in root and canal configurations depend on several factors, including ethnicity, age, and gender of the population studied. Among all teeth, mandibular second premolars are considered some of the most challenging to treat endodontically due to their highly variable root anatomy.¹

Mandibular second premolars are usually single rooted and have a single canal in more than 95% of cases. However, rare variations, including the presence of two roots with one canal each, have been reported with low incidence rates ranging from 0.3% to 1.9%.^{2,3,4} Missed anatomy, particularly untreated canals or roots, remains a common cause of failure in previously treated teeth.⁵ This case report highlights the successful non-surgical re-treatment of a two-rooted mandibular second premolar (tooth 45), previously mismanaged due to unrecognized anatomical variation.

Case Report

A 65 year old female patient named Varisha reported to the Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, Shree Bankey Bihari Dental College, Ghaziabad,

with a chief complaint of dull, continuous pain in the lower right back region of the jaw for the past one week.

The pain was aggravated by mastication and relieved only upon taking medication. The patient gave a dental history of root canal treatment in the mandibular right second premolar (tooth 45) approximately two weeks prior.

A preoperative intraoral periapical radiograph (Figure 1) revealed a previously treated tooth with a single obturated canal. However, a second root and canal had been missed, and periapical radiolucency was evident, indicating apical pathology. Upon re-entry and thorough assessment, two separate roots were identified, each containing a single canal.

Figure 1: Pre operative radiograph

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Treatment Procedure

Local anaesthesia was administered, and tooth 45 was isolated using a rubber dam. The previous restoration was removed, and the access cavity was refined, revealing a previously missed distal root canal. Hedström (H) files were used to remove the existing gutta-percha manually.

Both mesial and distal canals were negotiated using a #10 K-file, and working length was determined with an apex locator and confirmed radiographically (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Working Length Radiograph showing separate mesial and distal canals in tooth 45.

Cleaning and shaping were performed using Dentsply ProTaper Gold rotary instruments. Both canals were prepared up to F1 (20/.07 taper). Irrigation was carried out with copious amount of 2.5% Sodium Hypochlorite (UPS Hygienes Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, Maharashtra, India), 17% EDTA (DeSmear, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India). Final rinse was done with sterile saline.

The canals were dried using paper points, and a creamy paste of calcium hydroxide was placed in both canals using a Lentulo spiral. The access cavity was temporarily sealed with Cavit-G, and the patient was recalled after 7 days.

Second Appointment: At the 7-day follow up, the patient was asymptomatic. The temporary restoration was removed, and canals were irrigated with normal saline and NaOCl to remove the intracanal medicament. Master cones were selected and verified radiographically (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Master Cone Radiograph

Obturation was completed using the single cone technique with gutta-percha and bioceramic sealer. A post-operative radiograph was taken to confirm the quality of the obturation (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Post-Obturation Radiograph

Discussion

Successful endodontic therapy relies on the complete debridement, disinfection, and three-dimensional obturation of the root canal system. One of the most common causes of endodontic failure is the presence of missed anatomy, particularly additional roots or canals.⁵ The mandibular second premolar is generally considered to have a single root and canal, making rare configurations such as two roots with separate canals a diagnostic challenge.

Cleghorn et al. reported that two rooted mandibular second premolars occur in approximately 0.3% to 1.9% of cases, making this a rare but clinically significant variation.³ These variations are often overlooked due to the limitations of conventional radiography and insufficient inspection during access preparation. Studies by Zillich and Dowson², and Kartal and Yanikoglu⁶, as well as CBCT based reviews by Patel et al.⁷, further support the existence and complexity of such variants.

Morphological diversity in lower premolars continues to receive growing clinical interest due to their wide range of anatomical presentations.⁸ Compared to mandibular first premolars, second premolars are less frequently documented in the literature. This scarcity of data can contribute to diagnostic uncertainty. For example, Arayasantiparb et al. found multiple roots in 5.73% of first premolars but observed no additional roots in second premolars within a Thai population.⁹ Similarly, Dosunmu et al. reported the prevalence of two rooted mandibular second premolars as low as 0.4%.¹⁰

In the present case, a previously untreated distal root and canal led to persistent symptoms and periapical pathology. Re-treatment was successfully performed using Dentsply ProTaper Gold rotary instrumentation, calcium hydroxide as an intracanal medicament, and a bioceramic sealer with the single cone obturation technique, each of which is supported by clinical literature for its effectiveness in disinfecting and sealing complex canal systems.^{11,12} The role of calcium hydroxide in eliminating microbial contamination and promoting periapical healing is well documented.¹³

This case emphasizes the importance of thorough radiographic interpretation, use of magnification, and modified access preparation in identifying uncommon anatomical configurations. Early recognition of such variations is essential to avoid

endodontic failure and ensure favorable treatment outcomes.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of careful evaluation and recognition of root canal anatomy in retreatment cases, particularly in mandibular second premolars, which may occasionally present with two roots and two canals. Missed anatomy remains a common cause of endodontic failure, and its identification is critical for successful outcomes. Conservative non-surgical retreatment, supported by effective cleaning, shaping, and obturation techniques, can resolve persistent periapical pathology and restore function without surgical intervention.

References

1. Pathak VK, Soni S, Chouhan AS, Mankeliya S. Endodontic Treatment of a Mandibular Second Premolar with Type IV Vertucci Root Canal Configuration: A Case Report. *TMU J DENT* 2018; 5 (3): 23-24.
2. Zillich R, Dowson J. Root canal morphology of mandibular first and second premolars. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1973; 36 (5): 738-744.
3. Cleghorn BM, Christie WH, Dong CC. Root and root canal morphology of the human permanent mandibular second premolar: a literature review. *J Endod.* 2007; 33 (9): 1031-1037.
4. Hiremath MC, Srivastava P. Bilateral two rooted mandibular second premolar: Report of an unusual case. *J Dent Med Sci.* 2015; 14: 117-20.
5. Hoen MM, Pink FE. Contemporary endodontic retreatments: an analysis based on clinical treatment findings. *J Endod.* 2002; 28 (12): 834-836.
6. Kartal N, Yanikoglu FC. Root canal morphology of mandibular incisors, lateral incisors, and premolars in a Turkish population. *J Endod.* 1992; 18 (11): 562-4.
7. Patel S, Durack C, Abella F, Roig M, Shemesh H, Lambrechts P, Lemberg K. Cone beam computed tomography in Endodontics a review. *Int Endod J.* 2015; 48 (1): 3-15.
8. Deviant morphology of the root canal system in mandibular premolars: clinical cases. Georgiev K, Pecheva A. *Folia Med.* 2022; 28:176-180. doi: 10.3897/folmed.64.e58877.
9. Prevalence and morphology of multiple roots, root canals and C-shaped canals in mandibular premolars from cone beam computed tomography images in a Thai population. Araya-santiparb R, Banomyong D. *J Dent Sci.* 2021; 16: 201-207. doi: 10.1016/j.jds.2020.06.010.
10. Mandibular premolars with multiple roots: a case report. Dosunmu OO, Sulaiman AO, Olasemi FS. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/26259162/> Niger Postgrad Med J. 2015; 22: 126-128.
11. Zhang W, Li Z, Peng B. Assessment of a new root canal sealer's apical sealing ability. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod.* 2009; 107 (6): e79-82.
12. Peters OA. Current challenges and concepts in the preparation of root canal systems: a review. *J Endod.* 2004; 30 (8): 559-567.
13. Mohammadi Z, Dummer PMH. Properties and applications of calcium hydroxide in endodontics and dental traumatology. *Int Endod J.* 2011; 44 (8): 697-730.